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Proteomic analysis identifies a stromal-enriched breast cancer subtype with clinical relevance for carboplatin treatment

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Abstract

Gene expression profiling and immunohistochemistry-based classification inform prognosis and guide treatment decisions in breast cancer. Yet, quantitative proteomics may provide a deeper understanding of disease biology and uncover additional personalized treatment options. Here, we performed in-depth mass spectrometry-based proteomics of 320 clinical breast cancer samples from baseline and early on-treatment. Unsupervised consensus clustering identified three proteome subtypes defined as basal-, luminal- and stromal-enriched. The stromal-enriched subtype was characterized by high expression of stromal-cell proteins and markedly low expression of DNA damage repair proteins, indicating an impaired DNA damage response. Clinically, patients with these tumors showed significantly better treatment response and survival when carboplatin was added to standard neoadjuvant chemotherapy. Finally, we validated the identification of the three clusters in two independent clinical cohorts and verified the low DNA damage repair protein expression in the stromal-enriched tumors. Our proteomic analysis identified novel breast cancer subgroups with clinical implications and thus underscores the clinical utility of proteomics for patient stratification in breast cancer.

Introduction

Breast cancer is routinely classified into three clinical subtypes based on immunohistochemical (IHC) assessment of estrogen receptor (ER), progesterone receptor (PgR) and human epidermal growth factor receptor 2 (HER2). Molecular stratification using the PAM50 gene expression signature offers more advanced diagnosis and refined recurrence risk predictions compared to conventional IHC-based classification (1-3). However, PAM50 subtyping does not always translate into actionable therapeutic decisions. As proteomics has recently become comparable in analytical depth and accuracy to gene expression profiling, it has been proposed to more reliably reveal functional phenotypic differences that underpin breast cancer heterogeneity (4-6). These advancements can enable more precise characterization of the tumor phenotype and add a functional level to the information used for guidance of treatment selection.

Neoadjuvant carboplatin is part of the preferred treatment approach in high-risk (stage II-III) triple negative breast cancer (TNBC) (7-10). While the use of carboplatin in ER-positive breast cancer has not demonstrated favorable clinical response (11, 12), the number of clinical trials for this patient cohort is limited. Carboplatin induces DNA damage by forming cross links which results in double strand breaks (DSBs) (13). Breast and ovarian cancer with aberrant DNA repair mechanisms have been proposed sensitive to carboplatin, particularly those with germline mutations in BRCA1/2 (gBRCA) which can cause homologous recombination deficiency (HRD) (14-16). Several clinical trials have reported increased response rates from chemotherapy in gBRCA or HRD patients, but the specificity for carboplatin is unclear (17-19). Carboplatin has also been proposed to have immune-modulating effects and whether it triggers immunogenic cell death (ICD) is debated (20). After the successful Keynote-522 clinical trial, carboplatin is now routinely used with pembrolizumab, PD-1 inhibitor, in stage II-III TNBC (21). However, not all patients benefit from the treatment. Despite extensive efforts to identify predictive markers of carboplatin response, robust clinical biomarkers are lacking.

In this study, we present multimodal proteomic analyses of ER-positive and TNBC tumors longitudinally sampled from patients treated with neoadjuvant chemotherapy with or without carboplatin (Cb+NACT vs. NACT). The tumors were profiled with mass spectrometry (MS) for unbiased proteomic analysis and reverse phase protein array (RPPA) to explore signaling pathways with phospho-proteomics. We demonstrate that a proteome-defined patient subgroup, characterized by high expression of stromal related proteins, has significant benefit from treatment with Cb+NACT compared to NACT alone. Based on our findings, we propose potential biomarkers to guide neoadjuvant carboplatin treatment in breast cancer.

Materials and methods

Patient cohort

The neoadjuvant I-BCT-1 clinical trial included 187 patients with early locally advanced HER2-negative breast cancer. The patients were randomized 1:1 to receive neoadjuvant paclitaxel alone or in combination with carboplatin for 12 weeks followed by epirubicin and cyclophosphamide for 12 weeks (NACT vs Cb+NACT). Breast tumor tissue was collected at baseline (W0), week 3 (W3) and week 12 (W12) on treatment. Pathological response was determined at time of surgery by pathological complete response (pCR) and the residual cancer burden (RCB) method. The latter assesses the extent of tumor remaining in the breast and lymph nodes (22), where pCR equals RCB 0. Response to treatment was defined as pCR for TNBC cases and RCB 0/1 for ER-positive cases, which are associated with good prognosis in the respective clinical subtypes (23). DNA copy number and RNA sequencing profiles were acquired, and used for determining genomic HRD and PAM50 subtypes, respectively. HRD was defined as biallelic loss of function of BRCA1/BRCA2 and/or copy-numbers-based HRD-score ≥ 42 calculated with the *scarHRD* package in R (24). PAM50 subtypes were calculated using the method described in Parker et al. (2).

Preparation of protein lysates

Protein lysates were prepared from available fresh-frozen tissue biopsies (n = 178 at W0 and n = 176 at W3). Briefly, tissue samples were prepared by solubilizing tissue in lysis buffer (1% Triton X-100, 50mM HEPES, 150mM NaCl, 1.5mM MgCl₂, 1mM EGTA, 100mM NaF, 10mM Na pyrophosphate, 1mM Na₃VO₄, 10% glycerol) and homogenized with a Precellys® homogenizer. Protein concentrations were determined using bicinchoninic acid protein assay (BCA), and concentrations were adjusted to 1.5 $\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{L}$. Subsequently, the tumor protein lysates were analyzed by reverse-phase protein array (RPPA) and MS. Samples for RPPA were boiled with 2 % SDS for ten minutes before analysis.

Data independent acquisition (DIA) LC-MS/MS-based proteomics

MS data acquisition from protein lysates was performed by the Clinical Proteomics Mass Spectrometry facility, Karolinska University Hospital, Science for Life laboratory. Protein lysate samples were preprocessed using a modified version of the SP3 protein clean up and digestion protocol (25). Tryptic peptides were separated with liquid chromatography (LC) using NanoElute autosampler LC system (Bruker, Bremen, Germany). MS/MS data acquisition was operated in DIA parallel accumulation-serial fragmentation (diaPASEF) mode with a mass range between 300-1700 m/z and peptides isolated using a 31 m/z window for each ion mobility window. The samples were analyzed in two rounds of diaPASEF LC-MS/MS, with W0 samples in round 1 and W3 samples and 30 technical replicates from W0 (for subsequent batch correction) in round 2. A pooled sample containing peptides from 18 different tumor samples was used to generate DIA library for peptide-centric analysis analyzed in data-dependent acquisition (DDA) mode. Spectra from DDA for DIA library and both rounds of diaPASEF were searched using Spectronaut 16.2.220903.53000 (Biognosys).

In total, 10717 proteins were quantified across 389 samples. Proteins quantified in less than 50% of the samples were filtered out, and samples with less than 70% of total proteins quantified were

filtered out. Data was log₂-transformed and median centered over samples. Missing values were imputed as missing not at random (MNAR) using R package *imputeLCMD* with R function *impute.MinProb*. The data from the two rounds were batch corrected by fitting a linear regression curve for each protein of the 30 technical replicates in each round, and corrected protein intensities calculated for the round 2 dataset. The resulting dataset consisted of 7876 proteins quantified in 164 patient samples at W0 and 156 patient samples at W3.

RPPA proteomics

RPPA proteomics of 494 cancer-relevant proteins (including total- and phosphoproteins) was measured by the RPPA core facility at MD Anderson Cancer Center (Houston, TX, USA) (26). Lysates were serially diluted in 5 two-fold dilutions with lysis buffer and printed on nitrocellulose-coated slides using an Aushon Biosystems 2470 arrayer. Slides were probed with 494 validated primary antibodies followed by detection with appropriate biotinylated secondary antibodies. The relative protein levels for each sample were determined and normalized for protein loading. Five samples were removed in the subsequent analysis because of inadequate normalization.

Pathway activity scores of signaling pathways calculated for each sample were determined by summarizing protein levels of all proteins positively associated with the pathway and subtracting the protein levels of all proteins negatively associated with the pathway, as previously described (27, 28). In addition to the already defined pathways, a pathway activity score for interferon signaling (INF) was defined based on overlapping proteins in the Ayers et al. INF signature (29) and including cGAS and STING for type I INF signaling. All proteins involved in the pathway activity scores are given in supplementary table SX.

K-means consensus clustering

The 20% most variable proteins in the W0 MS dataset were used for k-means consensus clustering. Clustering was performed using function *ConsensusClusterPlus* in R package *ConsensusClusteringPlus* with parameters: k = 2-6, reps = 1000, distance = “Euclidean”. The optimal number of clusters was determined by examining consensus matrices and change in cumulative distribution function (CDF) area.

Gene set enrichment and variation analysis (GSEA and GSVA)

To condense information from the MS proteome data to pathways or signature summaries, GSEA and GSVA were performed (30, 31). Differential expression analysis was performed between relevant groups using function *lmFit* with R package *limma* on the MS datasets. GSEA was performed using function *fgsea* with R package *fgsea* using reference gene sets from the Hallmarks database retrieved with the *msigdb* function in R package *msigdb*. GSVA estimates the variation of pathway activity over a sample population and was performed using functions *gsvaParam* and *gsva* with R package *GSVA*.

NeoAva and CPTAC proteomic data validation cohorts

Two proteomic datasets were used to validate findings: RPPA proteomics from the NeoAva clinical trial (32), and MS proteomics from the CPTAC breast tumor cohort (33). NeoAva is an “in-house” clinical trial in which the patients received similar backbone NACT as in I-BCT. RPPA protein expression data from pre-treatment are available from Haugen et al. (34). CPTAC MS and

metadata were retrieved from Krug et al. (33). Proteins with less than 50% detection rate were filtered out. Where multiple genes were identified, the protein with highest variance was selected. Missing values were imputed using function *impute.MinProb* in R package *imputeLCMD*, and data were subsequently median centered over samples.

Statistical analysis

For continuous variables, pairwise comparisons were performed using two-sample t-test or Mann Whitney U test if data did not meet assumption of normality. For comparisons with more than two groups, ANOVA and TukeyHSD post-test were used to determine which groups were statistically significantly different. For categorical variables, comparisons between groups were performed using Fisher's exact test. Event-free and overall survival were analyzed with the Kaplan-Meier methods and Cox regression models using package *survival* in R. A p-value < 0.05 was used as cutoff for statistical significance. All calculations were performed in R using R-studio with R version 4.3.1. Figures were generated using R package *ggplot2*.

Results

Proteomic analysis of breast cancer tissue samples

Tumor samples collected at baseline (W0) and week 3 (W3) on-treatment from patients included in the I-BCT clinical trial were profiled with MS (n = 164 at W0 and n = 156 at W3) and RPPA (n = 173 at W0). We examined whether W0 MS proteome data recapitulated PAM50 classification of the samples by principal component analysis (PCA). There was a clear separation between the basal-like samples and Luminal A and B samples by the second principal component (Figure 1a). The first principal component did not separate the samples based on known subtypes and suggested that the MS data could uncover unknown subtypes.

Consensus clustering reveals distinct breast cancer subtypes

To identify protein-based subtypes, unsupervised consensus clustering was performed on the top 20% variant proteins in the W0 MS dataset (n = 1576 proteins). Three robustly segregated groups were identified based on assessment of consensus matrices and change in CDF area (Figure 1b, Supplementary Fig S1). The clusters partially recapitulated PAM50 and IHC classification (Figure 1c, Supplementary Table S1). Cluster-1 (n = 64) consisted predominantly of PAM50-classified basal-like samples (n = 59). Within this cluster there were 48 TNBC and 16 ER-positive cases. Cluster-2 (n = 71) was enriched for luminal samples (n = 42 Luminal A, n = 23 Luminal B) and the vast majority were ER-positive (n = 69). Cluster-3 (n = 29) consisted of a mix of PAM50 subtypes and encompassed both TNBC (n = 11) and ER-positive (n = 18) cases.

Functional characterization identifies basal-, luminal- and stromal-enriched proteome subtypes

Since Cluster-3 was not distinguished by the known PAM50 and IHC-classification, protein signaling in the clusters was examined by gene set enrichment analysis (GSEA) of differentially expressed proteins in each cluster compared to the others (Figure 1d). As expected, Cluster-1 had increased signaling of typical basal-like gene sets such as G2M checkpoint, E2F targets and MYC targets. In addition, this cluster was significantly enriched for immune-related gene sets: interferon alpha (INF α) and gamma response (INF γ), allograft rejection, and tumor-necrosis-factor (TNF)/nuclear factor kB (NF-kB) essential for activation of T-cells and effector T-cell differentiation (35). Cluster-2 was enriched for pathways typical for luminal/ER-positive breast cancer, such as ER signaling early and late, fatty acid metabolism and androgen signaling. Cluster-3 was enriched for stromal gene sets such as coagulation, epithelial-mesenchymal transition (EMT), myogenesis, angiogenesis and hypoxia.

Protein signaling in the clusters were further described by functional proteomics using RPPA. The identified proteome subtypes were clearly separated by the first and second principal components using all RPPA-measured proteins, showing a general agreement between the MS and RPPA datasets (Supplementary Fig S2). Cluster-1 (basal-enriched) had significantly ($p < 0.001$) higher expression activity of G2M checkpoint (Figure 1e). Cluster-2 (luminal-enriched) had significantly ($p < 0.001$) higher expression activity of hormone receptors. Cluster-3 had significantly higher expression of the core reactive and EMT pathway activity scores ($p < 0.001$). The core reactive pathway is defined by high expression of proteins expressed by stromal cells (such as Caveolin-1, Collagen etc.) (36). By both MS and RPPA proteomics, Cluster-3 was

therefore distinguished by high expression of extracellular-matrix, mesenchymal and stromal proteins. Taken together, consensus clustering of MS proteome data revealed three distinct subtypes identified as basal-enriched, luminal-enriched and stromal-enriched.

Patients with basal- and stromal-enriched tumors have clinical benefit from Cb+NACT

Examination of treatment response revealed differences in outcomes and benefit from carboplatin across the three subtypes. The addition of carboplatin significantly increased the fraction of patients that achieved pCR for patients with basal-enriched tumors ($p = 0.02$) (Figure 2a). The pCR fraction was low in the luminal-enriched subtype in both treatment arms. Interestingly, addition of carboplatin also increased the pCR fraction in the stromal-enriched subtype (50% with Cb+NACT against 21% with NACT alone). Since minimal residual disease (RCB 1) at surgery is similarly associated with prolonged prognosis as pCR in ER-positive breast cancer (23, 37), we defined responders as those that achieved pCR for TNBC cases and RCB 0/1 for ER-positive cases. The same trend was observed (Figure 2b) with this response definition: patients with basal- and stromal-enriched tumors had a significant increase in response rate from addition of carboplatin ($p = 0.01$ and $p = 0.02$, respectively).

Notably, the stromal-enriched subtype displayed the most favorable event-free survival (EFS) and overall survival (OS) outcomes when treated with Cb+NACT, with no events in this treatment arm ($p = 0.01$, cox proportional hazard) (Figure 2c, d). In the basal-enriched subtype, addition of carboplatin also increased EFS and OS: 93% EFS with Cb+NACT against 72% with NACT arm at 2 years, while not significantly. Conversely, the luminal-enriched subtype derived no benefit from Cb+NACT for EFS or OS.

Distinct immune activation during NACT in the proteome subtypes

Changes in protein signaling early on treatment may reveal important information on how tumors respond and possible resistance mechanisms. Treatment induced changes were explored with GSVA within the identified consensus clusters comparing W0 and W3 in each treatment arm (Figure 3a). Enrichment of tumor-intrinsic hallmark gene sets such as G2M checkpoint and ER response early decreased in all three subtypes from W0 to W3, while TME and stroma related gene sets increased. This was regardless of the baseline activation across the proteome subtypes and treatment arm. Notably, enrichment of immune-related Hallmark gene sets increased from W0 to W3 in basal- and stromal-enriched tumors, whereas these gene sets remained depleted in luminal-enriched tumors.

Due to the differences in immune activation across the subtypes, immune activity in responders and non-responders was further explored. Basal- and stromal-enriched tumors had significantly higher RPPA pathway activity score of interferon signaling (INF) in responders compared to non-responders (Figure 3b). In basal-enriched tumors, responders were enriched for INF γ , INF α and allograft rejection and the gene sets remained enriched at W3 (Figure 3c). The basal-enriched non-responders had low enrichment of these gene sets at baseline, but activity increased at W3. In stromal-enriched tumors, immune activity was higher and increased from W0 to W3 in responders while constant in non-responders. The immune activity in luminal-enriched tumors was low and remained constant or decreased in both responders and non-responders. The results suggest that tumors with a basal- or stromal-enriched subtype were more susceptible to immune infiltration and activation from chemotherapy treatment than luminal-enriched tumors.

Impaired DNA damage response in basal- and stromal-enriched tumors

Carboplatin's mechanism of action is induction of apoptosis through generation of DNA DSBs. Therefore, DNA repair mechanisms were explored in the proteome subtypes. The fraction of genomic HRD-positive tumors and the HRD score were significantly higher in the basal-enriched subtype compared to the other subtypes ($p < 0.001$), indicating an impaired HR repair in these tumors (Figure 4a). In this subtype, HRD score was higher in responders to both Cb+NACT and NACT, although not significantly (Supplementary Fig S5). RPPA pathway activity scores revealed that the basal- and stromal-enriched tumors had significantly higher activity of DNA damage checkpoint signaling compared to the luminal-enriched tumors (Figure 4b). The stromal-enriched subtype also had a significant decrease in expression of DNA repair proteins, which could indicate an impaired DNA damage response in this subtype (Figure 4c).

In agreement with RPPA, the MS data demonstrated that Hallmark gene set DNA repair was depleted in the stromal-enriched subtype at W0 (Figure 4d). In the other subtypes, enrichment of DNA repair decreased from W0 to W3, while p53 pathway increased. Notably, apoptosis activity increased from W0 to W3 in tumors with basal-enriched subtype, while persistently low in luminal-enriched tumors, indicating how the tumors respond to treatment.

Because of the differences in DNA repair mechanisms between basal- and stromal-enriched tumors, we compared the RPPA protein expression in responders to Cb+NACT (Figure 4e). Proteins in DNA damage checkpoint were not differentially expressed in the two responder groups, while DNA damage repair proteins were lower expressed in stromal-enriched tumors. Specifically, PARP-1 were among the top differentially expressed proteins in basal-enriched responders.

Identification of proteome clusters in NeoAva

To validate the identification of the proteomic subtypes, we used RPPA proteomics data from primary tumors from the NeoAva clinical trial. The data set consisted of a comparable patient cohort with TNBC ($n = 21$) and ER-positive cases ($n = 95$). The RPPA core reactive and hormone receptor activity scores were determined and used to identify the three proteome subgroups: luminal-, basal- and stromal-enriched (Figure 6a, b). By PCA, the first and second principal component separated the three subtypes well (Supplementary Fig. S5). The NeoAva clusters highly resembled the original clusters from the I-BCT cohort in terms of RPPA signaling pathway activity (Figure 6c). G2M checkpoint signaling was significantly lower ($p < 0.001$) and EMT signaling was significantly higher in the stromal-enriched tumors ($p < 0.001$) compared to basal- and luminal-enriched tumors. Consistent with our analysis of the I-BCT cohort, DNA damage checkpoint signaling was higher in basal- and stromal-enriched tumors compared to luminal-enriched and DNA damage repair signaling was significantly lower in the stromal-enriched tumors ($p < 0.001$).

Comparing differentially expressed proteins in stromal- and basal-enriched tumors revealed lower expression of PARP, XRCC1, and ERCC1 in stromal-enriched tumors. Inconsistent with the I-BCT cohort, expression of Rad51 was higher in stromal-enriched tumors compared to basal-enriched.

Identification of proteome clusters in CPTAC

To validate our findings using MS proteomics we used the TMT MS dataset from Krug et al, CPTAC, which consisted of a similar patient cohort. Consensus clustering of the CPTAC MS dataset was performed using the 1249 proteins that overlapped with the top 1576 variant proteins (top 20%) in the I-BCTW0 MS dataset. Based on inspection of consensus matrices and change in CDF area, three consensus proteome subgroups were identified (Supplementary Fig. S7). By PCA, the first and second principal component clearly separated the three clusters and partly recapitulated PAM50 classification (Figure 7a-c). Cluster-3 consisted mainly of LumA (n = 31) and normal-like samples (n = 3), and highly resembled the NMF-cluster LumA-I identified by Krug et al. (33).

Characterization of the clusters by GSEA revealed that Cluster-1, -2 and -3 highly resembled the basal, luminal- and stromal-enriched subtypes from the I-BCT cohort, respectively (Figure 7d). Consistent with the stromal-enriched I-BCT tumors, Cluster-3 was enriched for stromal gene sets such as EMT, coagulation, myogenesis, angiogenesis and hypoxia, and demonstrated high stromal infiltration score (Figure 7e). The DNA repair gene set was significantly depleted in this subtype, also in agreement with the I-BCT and the NeoAva cohort. Cluster-1, which resembled the basal-enriched subtype, demonstrated high immune cell infiltration score and chromosomal instability (CIN) score (Figure 7e).

Discussion

In this study, unsupervised clustering of MS proteomics revealed three proteome subtypes with distinct clinical outcomes from treatment with Cb+NACT compared to NACT. The pronounced differences in pathway enrichment between the three clusters support the concept that these are biologically distinct subtypes classified as basal-, luminal- and stromal-enriched.

Patients with basal- and stromal-enriched tumors had favorable treatment outcomes when carboplatin was added to standard NACT. From a clinical point of view, these findings are notable as both the basal- and stromal-enriched subtypes included ER-positive cases which are not as standard given neoadjuvant carboplatin today. Carboplatin mediates apoptosis through DNA damage from DNA crosslinks, and therefore, alterations in DNA repair mechanisms may lead to sensitivity and resistance to carboplatin. The high HRD rate in basal-enriched tumors can partly explain the high response rates in these patients (17, 18). Functional HRD by IHC-based RAD51 test has been shown to independently predict clinical benefit from adding carboplatin to NACT in TNBC and was highly concordant with genomic HRD test (38). Enhanced DNA repair capability is one of the potential resistance mechanisms for platinum-based treatment (13, 39). For example, cisplatin resistance has been associated with efficient removal of platinum from DNA by the nucleotide excision repair process, where ERCC1 and RPA are essential proteins (40, 41). The stromal-enriched subtype had low expression of DNA repair proteins, and this was further confirmed in the NeoAva and CPTAC cohort. This could indicate an impaired DNA damage response in the stromal-enriched tumors, not necessarily related to HRD as many tumors were HR proficient but still linked to sensitivity to carboplatin. In a recent study, single-cell proteomics of ovarian cancer cell lines identified “protein modules” which indicated distinct sensitivity or resistance to carboplatin (42). The sensitive module consisted of high expression of DNA damage checkpoint proteins such as pATM and γ H2AX, and low expression of DNA repair proteins such as PARP-1 and Rad51, in line with our findings of DNA repair protein signaling in the stromal-enriched subtype.

The stromal-enriched subtype consisted of a mix of PAM50 subtypes and thus illustrates the heterogeneity of breast tumors that exist beyond the established molecular subtypes. Stromal-enriched breast cancer has previously been identified using both MS and RPPA analysis. A multiomics study on 77 breast cancer patients from Mertins et al. identified basal-, luminal- and stromal-enriched subgroups by unsupervised consensus clustering of MS data (43). In agreement with our I-BCT cohort, the stromal-enriched subtype consisted of a mix of all PAM50 subtypes and showed high activity of core reactive signaling. Omitting protein data from their clustering did not identify the stromal-enriched subtype, implying that this subtype can only be detected at the protein level. In line with this, unsupervised clustering of RPPA data from 403 breast cancer samples identified in addition to the PAM50 subtypes, two novel subtypes named reactive I and II, describing stromal-rich tumors (44). It has been shown that the PAM50 gene signature lack markers describing features of the tumor stroma, such as hypoxia and angiogenesis (45). Taken together with our findings, this underscores the need for proteome data to acknowledge the stromal features for a better subtype stratification.

As luminal A tumors comprise a large proportion of breast cancers, they can still exhibit discordant prognostic risks and molecular heterogeneity. We validated the identification of our

three proteome subtypes using data from the NeoAva and the CPTAC cohorts, in which the stromal-enriched subtype consisted predominantly of Luminal A tumors. A stromal-rich subset within the luminal A subtype has previously been reported both in the original analysis of the CPTAC proteome data (33), and from consensus clustering of MS data from breast tumor samples (46). Stromal features of the TME have been proposed as a basis for subclassifying ER-positive breast cancer. However, prior studies have associated stromal-rich tumors with both favorable prognosis (36) and, when characterized by a “high-grade stroma”, with worse prognosis (47). These contradictory findings highlight the need for a more standardized and consensus-based approach to characterize tumor stroma for risk stratification in ER-positive breast cancer.

High INF signaling at baseline in the basal- and stromal-enriched tumors was significantly associated with response to treatment, although not specific for carboplatin. We also observed higher immune activity in these tumors, in which the patients responded to Cb+NACT, compared to the poorly responding luminal-enriched subtype. In concordance, the CALGB 40603 (Alliance) study demonstrated that responders to both Cb+NACT and NACT alone displayed features associated with the tumor immune microenvironment, including presence of T-, B- and NK-cells (48). In the GeparSixto clinical trial, tumor infiltrating lymphocytes and an mRNA immune score were associated with response to both Cb+NACT and NACT alone (49), while the authors emphasized carboplatin’s strong interaction with the immune system. The association with the GeparSixto immune score and response was further validated in the BrightNess study (50).

We profiled the protein landscape in tumors longitudinally, at both baseline and early on-treatment. The basal-enriched responders had high immune activity at baseline which was preserved on-treatment. In contrast, immune activity in the stromal-like tumors at baseline was lower, but increased on-treatment. This suggests a different ability to engage the immune microenvironment. The basal-enriched tumors are dominant by TNBC which are generally more immunoactive. The immune activity in the stromal-enriched subtype might be hindered by stromal components such as extracellular matrix or fibroblasts (51), and possibly, this suppression might be overcome by carboplatin treatment, as shown in a recent study (52). Other studies have shown that carboplatin enhances CD8+ T-cell trafficking into the tumor by affecting lymphocyte-endothelial interactions (53) and convert cold tumors into hot (54).

Our study has some limitations. Since there exists a limited number of clinical trials with carboplatin in ER-positive breast cancer together with proteomic profiling of tumor samples, we were unable to validate that the stromal-enriched subtype has a favorable response to carboplatin in an independent cohort. I-BCT is a phase II clinical trial, the sample sizes were therefore calculated based on pCR and RCB as primary endpoints. The study is therefore not powered to evaluate the impact of long-term outcomes. The sample size profiled with MS-based proteomics is large enough to represent the HER2-negative breast cancer population and enabled us to identify novel proteome subtypes. It should be noted that the three proteome subtypes had somewhat uneven sample sizes, and the power to detect subtype characteristics and outcome associations was therefore equivalently skewed.

Taken together, our study demonstrates that quantitative proteomics can uncover unknown biological subtypes of breast cancer with clinical relevance. We showed that the stromal-enriched subtype, which includes ER-positive tumors, may have benefit from treatment with neoadjuvant carboplatin likely due to an impaired DNA damage response. Further studies on

DNA repair mechanisms in ER-positive breast cancer could therefore possibly identify a patient subgroup that is sensitive to carboplatin.

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